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Research Article

A CROSS SECTIONAL STUDY ON THE EVALUATION OF INHALER USAGE TECHNIQUE AND ITS EFFECTS ON COPD AND ASTHMA PATIENTS

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Abstract:

Objective: The aim of this study was to evaluate the Inhaler use technique in the patients of Asthma or Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease.

Methodology: The design of this study was Cross Sectional Study. This study was conducted in Shaikh Zayed Hospital Raheem Yar Khan and the duration of this study was from January 2020 to April 2020. 80 patients having asthma or chronic obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) were selected for the research study. These patients were asked to show their way of using inhaler in the presence of a medical officer and all those patients had previous history of inhaler prescription. Medical officer observed various ways of inhaling through inhaler as carried out by the patients. Every participant filled a 10-step questionnaire specially designed for the research purpose which evaluated the inhalation technique of the participants, answers were given in the form of true and false as alternate choice questions. Demographic variables and data both were documented.

Results: No removal of cap was done by 6% of the patients, most of the participants shook the inhaler well before inhaling process (87.5%) and right upright position of inhaler was observed by (95%) of the patients. Gentle breathing was not carried out by 50% of the participants, inappropriate mouth sealing was not observed by the (32.5%), canister push breathing was carried out by (37.5%), after pressing canister simultaneously breathing was observed and holding of breath after the pushing of canister was observed by (42.5%). Single inhalation & single actuation was observed by (47.5%) of the participants. Majority of the cases (52.5%) in case of extra dose did not observe a gap of sixty seconds.

Conclusion: In-hand research outcomes reflect that patients were not aware about the basic steps of inhaler use and they failed to perform the basic steps required by the effective usage and dosage of the drug.

Key Words: Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease, Actuation, Canister, Asthma, Inflammation.

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INTRODUCTION:

Asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) are amongst the repeated respiratory situations along with intersecting characteristics of the disease. These clinical situations are attributed to air flow a rate of pulmonary path and almost reversible obstruction of airway in the patients of asthma, but in the case of COPD it is not completely reversible. In addition to that, because of airway increased inflammation chances are there that the patients may develop exacerbations of acute nature [1]. United States patients of young age reflected high rate of prevalence. In comparison to girls the asthma prevalence in boys is greater. Spirometry is considered as most repeated, practical, reliable and noninvasive lung test function, which establishes the severity and presence of disease that obstructs the airway [2]. An accurate diagnostic of asthma and COPD through different management methods for its treatment still has few common elements for the management of the both diseases. This include pharmacotherapy and modification of the lifestyle to control the severe conditions [3].

These disease treatment rages from anti-inflammatory to inhaled corticosteroids to orally taken medicines. Inhaled corticosteroids (ICSs) are used for the reduction of the airway inflammation and also considered as a key for the pharmacotherapy to treat asthma of persistent nature. Research studies have shown the effectiveness of the clinical nature as good for the various devices used for inhaling purposes in the inhaled corticosteroids delivery & Beta-II bronchodilators for COPD and asthma patients; however [4], focus was not given on the technique of inhaling by the affected individuals. COPD and asthma are counted as major problems of the health in our area and they cause poor quality of health. Majority of the cases are prescribed by the doctors to use inhalers for the management of both the diseases [5]. Because of poor or wrong technique, the treatment becomes in-effective and the spent money goes futile. The inappropriate technique adopted by the patients results in the form of financial loss, low dose inhaling and compromised treatment; to counter the issues we planned this research for the assessment and evaluation of the correct technique and trends of users about the use of inhalers.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The design of this study was Cross Sectional Study. This study was conducted in Shaikh Zayed Hospital Raheem Yar Khan and the duration of this study was

from January 2020 to April 2020. 80 patients having asthma or chronic obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) were selected for the research study. These patients were asked to show their way of using inhaler in the presence of a medical officer and all those patients had previous history of inhaler prescription. Medical officer observed various ways of inhaling through inhaler as carried out by the patients. Every participant filled a 10 step questionnaire specially designed for the research purpose which evaluated the inhalation technique of the participants, answers were given in the form of true and false as alternate choice questions [6]. Demographic variables and data both were documented. All the patients with not ready to participate, having chronic Diabetes Miletus, hepatic or renal disease were not included in the research paper. Permission of the hospital board and consent of the participants was secured before the start of the research. Inhalation technique steps were written as either "correct" or "false" and responses were documented. Removing inhaler cap, before use shaking, upright holding, gentle breathing out, effective sealing of mouth, coinciding inspiration (breathing in) and pushing the canister, continuous slow breathing after canister, breath holding, single actuation single inhalation and one minute before next inhaler action were steps included in the questionnaire.

RESULTS:

80 patients having asthma or chronic obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) were selected for the research study. Research findings in terms of educational background were illiterate, housewives, laborers, office workers, self-employed and students were respectively 52 (65%), 24 (30%), 34 (42.5%), 10 (12.5%), 10 (12.5%) and 2 (2.5%) as shown in Table-I. In terms of family history of inhaler use positive history was observed in 8 (10%) and who were trained for the sue of inhaler were 54 (67.5%). Inhaler was prescribed by the medical officer to 56 (70%) with Asthma; whereas, 24 (30%) were diagnosed COPD. It is shown in Figure-I, that maximum number of cases removed cap, did not remove cap, shook the inhaler, upright held the inhaler, gentle breathing out, not sealing mouth effectively, breathing while canister pushed, slow continued breathing, single actuation and single inhalation and no wait time to next inhale was observed in number and percentage respectively in 75 (93.7%), 5 (6%), 70 (87.5%), 76 (95%), 40 (50%), 26 (32.5%), 30 (37.5%), 34 (42.5%), 34 (42.5%), 38 (47.5%) and 42 (52.5%). Data entry process and analysis of the data was completed by SPSS-16.

Table I: Educational Status of Study Subjects. (N=80)

Education	Frequency	Percent
Illiterate	52	65
Primary	16	20
Matriculation	10	12.5
Intermediate	2	2.5
Total	80	100

DISCUSSION:

This research study was held for the assessment of the inhaler use by the patients of asthma and COPD; they were evaluated with the help of a questionnaire specifically designed for the particular research paper. It included very important question regarding the use of inhaler and the number of questions was ten [6]. Unsatisfactory practice was observed for the use of inhaler without interactive learning of the technique. Low educated patients were more inappropriate in the

use of inhaler use [7]. The Hand-Held Inhaler was operated without any training and inexpertly. Face to Face training of the use of inhaler was enhanced in collaboration with PMDI [8]. Previous research studies observed that dry powder inhaler was used correctly by 58.9% of the cases and pressurized inhalers were used correctly before training 31.1% [9]. Our research finds that not even a single individual performed every stage correctly. It was very interesting to note that 6% of the cases did not open the cap of the inhaler [10].

Number = 80 Action	Alternative Replies			
	Yes	Percentage	No	Percentage
Cap Removed	75	93.75	5	6.25
Shook Well	70	87.5	10	12.5
Held Upright	76	95	4	5
Breathed Out Gently	40	50	40	50
Effective Mouth Seal	26	32.5	54	67.5
Breath in the Pressed Canister	30	37.5	50	62.5
Continue Breath Slowly	34	42.5	46	57.5
Hold Breath	34	42.5	46	57.5
Single Actuation Single Inhalation	38	47.5	42	52.5
One Minute Wait Before Next Dose	38	47.5	42	52.5

The only reason that contributed to this action is lack of awareness in the subjects. Other reasons may include the old age of the patients and observational fear. Another research presents an overall number of 40% at least made one mistake in the use of inhaler. Devices comparison was also carried out and it was observed that dry powder devices were used relatively correct [11]. Chinese patients in another study reflected wrong technique of using inhaler in COPD cases.

93.8% of the subjects inaccurately observed step no eight as this step elaborates that make a force full inhalation in the initial stage and make it deep and slow and uniform as well, till the time lungs became full of inhale. Step number 8 was mostly mishandled [12]. On the contrary in our research outcomes the same step

number 8 was performed incorrectly and correctly respectively 34 (42%) and 46 (58%) patients. According to G Mustafa effective mouth sealing was ineffective [13]. Whereas, in our research the same step was performed by 54 (67%) patients. After three days regular training the score was improved in the use of inhaler use. Correct performances were also significant as control group was evaluated on 10th, 20th and 30th day respectively as (96.24% versus 85.63% and $p < 0.01$), (97.31% versus 86.09% and $p < 0.01$) and (98.19% versus 87.39% and $p < 0.01$) [14]. In other errors in the practice of inhaler was not shaking the inhaler and it was observed in 10 (13%) of the patients. Chinese patients also reflected errors in step number thirteen while they were diagnosed for inhaler by the medical officers in the diagnosis of COPD. Optimum results can be gained

through continuous education on the subject for better treatment results and management of the disease in the practice of Diskus inhaler [9].

We found in our research that basic essential steps were not being performed correct and drug was not delivered to the lungs effectively. Few of the patients were even not knowing the exact holding procedure of the inhaler. Few were this much unaware that even used the inhaler without opening it. 50% were not able to inhale an exhale properly as prescribed by the expert. One third of the subjects was not sealing their mouth effectively and they were not in the habit of pressing the canister of the inhaler at the same time when they were breathing. Another outcome of the research is that subjects were trained before the use of inhaler including male, laborers and illiterate by experts.

CONCLUSION:

In-hand research outcomes reflect that patients were not aware about the basic steps of inhaler use and they failed to perform the basic steps required by the effective usage and dosage of the drug.

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